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Authoritarian Liberalism and the Transformation of Modern Europe: Introduction

Michael A Wilkinson

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Abstract:

This book recounts the transformation of Europe from the interwar era until the euro crisis, using the tools of constitutional analysis and critical theory. Interwar liberalism, rocked by mass politics and social inequality, actively turns to authoritarianism in an attempt to suppress democracy, with disastrous consequences in Weimar and beyond. After the Second World War, economic liberalism is restored through a passive authoritarianism: inter-state sovereignty is restrained, state-society relations are depoliticised, and class struggle subdued. This transformation takes time to unfold and it presents continuities as well as discontinuities. It is deepened by the neoliberalism of the Maastricht era and yet counter-movements then also emerge, which are more actively repressed through the authoritarian liberalism of the euro crisis phase. This leads now to an impasse. If the postwar order of authoritarian liberalism has reached its limits, as suggested by the emergence of an authoritarian populism, there is yet to be any definitive rupture.

KEYWORDS: Authoritarian liberalism, European integration, transformation of Europe, euro-crisis, neoliberalism, authoritarian populism

Michael A Wilkinson is Associate Professor in the Department of Law, London School of Economics and Political Science

E-mail: M.Wilkinson@lse.ac.uk

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Accounts of European integration typically begin with reconstruction following the devastation of the continent in the first half of the 20th century. They begin by depicting a desire to start afresh, a *Stunde Null*, an attempt to ensure that the conflict of the preceding decades would never again happen. Blame for the preceding collapse is laid at the foot of a destructive nationalism, militarily aggressive and economically protectionist. The solution, directed primarily at Germany, is to tame the impulse to rearm and to encourage the drive towards market integration. The simultaneous fulfillment of both aims, peace and prosperity, is symbolized by the Treaty of Paris of 1951 and its creation: the supranational institutions and structures that would be the hallmark of the European Union over the following sixty years.¹

This book does not reject that story in its entirety but it does offer an alternative explanation, one that highlights what that account misses and why, from a constitutional perspective, that omission is significant. In short, Europe is reconstituted, from the very beginning of the postwar period, in reaction to the fear of democracy, which had threatened to unleash itself in the interwar period. This is significant because it suggests that the ‘democratic deficit’ identified since Maastricht, and described as a ‘democratic default’ in the euro-crisis phase, is not merely a symptom of recent decades of neoliberalism, but characteristic of a far deeper condition.² It is also significant because it suggests that any

*Associate Professor of Law, LSE. This is the introduction to my book *Authoritarian Liberalism and the Transformation of Modern Europe* (OUP 2021).

¹ The two dominant narratives of integration are functionalist, focusing on economic interdependencies, and intergovernmentalist, focusing on inter-state bargaining. Joseph Weiler adds a structural as well as ideological, messianic, component (see ‘The Political and Legal Culture of Integration: An Exploratory Essay’ (2011) 9:3-4 *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 678 – 694) and Luuk van Midelaar adds a normative vision, a ‘Europe of Citizens’ (based on an ideal of constitutionalism, in *The Passage To Europe: How a Continent Became a Union* (Yale University Press, 2013). Critical and material analysis has been marginal.

² See Giandomenico Majone, ‘From a Regulatory State to a Democratic Default’ (2014) *JCMS* 1- 8. The seminal pre-crisis work on the democratic deficit is Simon Hix and Andreas Follesdal, ‘Why there is a democratic

remedy to that deficit would require a radical constitutional re-imagination, or even a rupture from the postwar constitutional settlement.

It is hardly novel to argue that postwar Europe is conditioned by a fear of democracy, and hence by the perceived need for it to be ‘constrained’. Jan-Werner Müller has presented this claim in detail, describing various formal and informal strategies designed to restructure existing institutions and create new ones, domestic as well as European, in order to build a constitutional architecture that de-politicises the activity of governing.³ Müller’s focus was on the cultural and political disciplining of mass democracy in postwar reconstruction in general, and the significance of the Christian Democratic movement in achieving this goal in particular.⁴ In his account, the postwar settlement was designed to discipline and stabilize liberal democracy, to prevent it from committing ‘democratic suicide’. Much related work on the so-called ‘counter-majoritarian’ dilemma (including the inappositely named ‘militant democracy’) focuses on the supposed internal contradiction between the two poles of ‘liberal democracy’ and considers how to prevent democratic majorities from pursuing goals that would undermine liberalism.⁵ Müller’s insights have yet to be fully integrated into a

deficit in the EU: A response to Majone and Moravcsik’ (2006) 44 *JCMS* 533 – 62. But earlier still, see Jürgen Habermas, ‘Remarks on Dieter Grimm’s ‘Does Europe Need a Constitution’ (1995) 1 *European Law Journal* 303 – 307 and Weiler, Haltern, Meyer, ‘European Democracy and its Critique’ (1995) 18 *West European Politics* 4.

³ See Jan-Werner Müller, *Contesting Democracy: Political Ideas in 20th Century Europe* (Yale University Press 2011). The claim is supported by much recent work in legal history on the origins of the integration project, see e.g. Antonin Cohen, ‘Constitutionalism without Constitution: Transnational Elites Between Mobilisation and Legal Expertise in the Making of a Constitution For Europe (1940’s-1960’s)’ (2007) 32 *Law and Social Enquiry* 109; Antoine Vauchez, ‘The Transnational Politics of Judicialisation: *Van Gend en Loos* and the Making of the EU Polity’ (2010) 16 *European Law Journal* 1.

⁴ Müller, *ibid*, ch 4.

⁵ The term ‘militant democracy’ was coined in 1935 by Karl Loewenstein. For two recent critical readings, see C Accetti and I Zuckerman, ‘What’s Wrong with Militant Democracy?’ (2017) 65:1 *Political Studies* 182 – 199 and A Malkopoulou and L Norman, ‘Three Models of Democratic Self-Defence: Militant Democracy and Its Alternatives’ (2018) 66:2 *Political Studies* 442 – 458.

constitutional history of the twentieth century, albeit that many of them were anticipated by the work of Carl Schmitt and since forgotten or discarded by liberal jurists.⁶

The focus here, however, is different: rather than the supposed internal contradiction in liberal democracy (and on the paradox of democratic self-destruction and the conceptual gymnastics involved in trying to resolve this), the critical issue is the material tension between democracy and capitalism. It is this heuristic that provides the explanatory framework for constitutional change.⁷

A critical, historical and theoretical lens is used to analyse the object of this study: the material constitution of the state and the regional order in Europe and its reconstitution through the postwar period. The material constitution is a complex assemblage of ordering forces and structures - political unity, institutional power, social relations and political-economic objectives.⁸ Aspects of these, which are internally related to formal constitutional norms, will be developed throughout the chapters. At this stage, the object can be presented in simplified form as a representation of the relation between the political and the economic realms.⁹ Getting to grips with the way this relation is reconstituted - through geopolitics and law, ideology and class interests - is key to understanding the transformation of Europe

⁶ See Benjamin Schupmann, *Carl Schmitt's State and Constitutional Theory* (OUP, 2017).

⁷ Although associated with the work of Wolfgang Streek (see e.g. *Buying Time: On the Delayed Crisis of Democratic Capitalism*), the dynamic tension has a deeper history in the Marxist tradition, see e.g. Ellen Meiksins Wood, *Democracy Against Capitalism: Renewing Historical Materialism* (CUP, 1995).

⁸ See Marco Goldoni and Michael A. Wilkinson, 'The Material Constitution' (2018) *Modern Law Review*. For a different kind of attempt to get beneath the 'visible architecture' of the EU and capture its 'political metaphysics' see Eva Nanopoulos and Fotis Vergis, 'The Inherently Undemocratic EU Democracy' in Nanopoulos and Vergis (eds.) *The Crisis Behind the EuroCrisis: On the Multi-Systemic Failure of the EU* (Cambridge University Press, 2019).

⁹ It is significant that ordoliberalism is hardly given a mention in Müller's *Contesting Democracy*, even though elsewhere Müller himself describes its significance in postwar Germany as immense. Ordoliberalism will be discussed in chapter 3 but it is immediately apparent that ordoliberalism does place centre stage the relation between the political and the economic, and also that it has been largely neglected until relatively recently.

in the 20th and 21st centuries, and its significance for constitutional theory. Or so it will be argued.

The argument presented in this book, in condensed form, is that the postwar European state system undergoes a structural transformation, a re-differentiation of the political and the economic spheres. Specifically, this relation is transformed through a conditioning of democratic sovereignty over the economy by taking economic matters out of the public domain of democratic power and accountability. The label ‘authoritarian liberalism’ is used to capture this phenomenon, a conjunction of political authoritarianism and economic liberalism.¹⁰ To reduce it to its most basic formulation, it captures the phenomenon of a liberalism that is pursued by authoritarian means, avoiding robust democratic accountability. It is liberal in the sense that it de-politicises the economy, naturalizes inequalities, and promotes markets, competition and private ownership.

Again, the claim that postwar Europe is conditioned by an attempt to reconstruct the tradition of classical liberalism initially through a mixed or ‘embedded version’ is not new.¹¹ The literature, however, rarely approaches this reconstruction in a critical manner or in a way that maps its trajectory. Authoritarian liberalism begins in the interwar period and then develops in a constitutional dynamic across various stages, beginning with the Treaties of Paris 1951 and of Rome 1957, gathering pace through the Single European Act 1986 and the Treaty of Maastricht 1992, and accelerating in an extraordinary manner through the euro-crisis phase (2008 -). The book concludes that Europe has reached a critical juncture,

¹⁰ I have developed this argument in a series of pieces, see Michael A. Wilkinson, ‘The Specter of Authoritarian Liberalism: Reflections on the Constitutional Crisis of the European Union’ (2013) 14 *German Law Journal* 527 - 560; ‘Authoritarian Liberalism in the European Constitutional Imagination: Second Time as Farce?’ (2015) 21 *European Law Journal* 313 - 339; ‘The Reconstitution of Postwar Europe: Liberal Excesses, Democratic Deficiencies’ in Dowdle and Wilkinson (eds.) *Constitutionalism Beyond Liberalism* (Cambridge University Press, 2017) and ‘Authoritarian Liberalism: The Conjuncture Behind the Crisis’ in Nanopoulos and Vergis (eds.) *The Crisis Behind the EuroCrisis: On the Multi-Systemic Failure of the EU* (Cambridge University Press, 2019).

¹¹ See e.g. John Gillingham, *European Integration: 1950 – 2003 Superstate or New Market Economy?* (Cambridge University Press, 2003).

entrapped in a fractious position, unable to move forward or backward.¹² Authoritarian liberalism is now fomenting the politics of an authoritarian populism that it was meant to prevent but with which it appears to be mutually dependent.

Delimiting the claim

A few words of caution are required about the nature of the claim made here. The postwar reconstitution of the European state and state-system occurs gradually. It does not follow a strictly linear progression or affect the entire continent in the same way. It is varied, uneven, and combined across European states. Although the EU plays a significant role, it is not related exclusively to the project or institutions of the EU; it is as much a phenomenon of domestic constitutional change as it is international and supranational. Indeed, I argue, as have others, that these layers are inseparable: European integration is a process of state transformation, more than it is the building of an independent set of institutions and structures above or separate from the state.¹³

A different kind of study might attempt to trace several constitutional ideal types with related but distinct trajectories as they emerge in different constitutional cultures and at different historical moments, developing a kind of ‘varieties of constitutionalism’ literature for the European Union. At least four might be identified. The first, ‘core Europe’, would consist in those countries having direct experience of the collapse of liberalism

¹² See Claus Offe, *Europe Entrapped* (Polity Press, 2014).

¹³ See especially Chris Bickerton, *European Integration: From Nation-state to Member State* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013). From a constitutional perspective, see also Erik Fossum and Agustin Menendez, *The Constitution’s Gift: A Constitutional Theory for a Democratic European Union* (Rowman & Littlefield, 2011). For an overview of the literature, see Eva Nanopoulos and Fotis Vergis, ‘The Inherently Undemocratic EU Democracy’ in Nanopoulos and Vergis (eds) *The Crisis Behind the Eurocrisis* (Cambridge University Press, 2019).

through the capitulation to fascism (the founding ‘six’). For this first group, European integration is not a simple choice, an experiment which could as well be reversed, or a club which could be joined or left at will; it is in the ‘DNA’ of their postwar constitutional identity, an escape from the burden of sovereignty. And Europe, in turn, bears the imprint of this identity given the significance of the founding six on its form. The second, a Southern fringe comprising Spain, Portugal and Greece, would consist in those countries that applied to join the Union following postwar dictatorship. For these countries, entry to the EU signposted the promised land of political liberalism.¹⁴ A third, comprising countries of the former Eastern bloc, would consist in those countries for whom EU membership signaled readmission to ‘the West’, an idea of Europe involving a rapid embrace of market capitalism, but also their reclaiming of sovereignty after decades of subjugation by an imperial power. For each of these three groups, the idea of ‘Europe’, in different ways, represents a form of emancipation from the past, perhaps with decreasing depths of attachment. A fourth and final category, more detached still, would consist in the sustained democracies of the UK and the Nordic countries, for whom EU membership was always less than wholehearted as a constitutional choice and signaled a more pragmatic stance – nothing fateful, still less emancipatory was signified. In none of this fourth group had the decline of parliamentary democracy in the interwar (or postwar) period been as severe, in none was the burden of the past as great. From that vantage point, particularly the UK, Europe may be properly viewed as a voluntary project.¹⁵

A full evaluation of the significance for comparative constitutional law of these regional and culturally specific varieties, and the obvious objections and exceptions to which

¹⁴ Ireland might belong or relate to this group, in the sense that its successful independence from the UK is strongly associated with membership of the EU.

¹⁵ Even for the UK, a strong voluntarism may be misleading. For the UK, membership of the EU has been presented as a significant aspect of its path to constitutional modernization. See e.g. Martin Loughlin, ‘The British Constitution: Thoughts on the Causes of the Present Discontents’ (2018) 16:1 *New Zealand Journal of Public and International Law*. But the modernization narrative does not capture the constitutional imagination in the same way as association of Europe with political emancipation.

they would give rise, would require several book-length studies. The argument here will distill a complex and varied set of constitutional histories into one singular theory and constitutional trajectory: a path of authoritarian liberalism. It is a trajectory that now comes under sustained pressure, not just from a single source, but from across the spectrum of political positions and across the geographical spread of the continent. The collapse of centrist parties (and rise of parties of the right and, to a lesser extent, the left), in particular, has affected countries belonging to all four ‘varieties of constitutionalism’.¹⁶ Authoritarian liberalism intertwines in different ways with each particular constitutional trajectory. But the commonalities are enough to demand a more comprehensive thesis.

Authoritarian liberalism

The label ‘authoritarian liberalism’ may confound, both in a conceptual and a historical sense.¹⁷ Although it is not uncommon to consider neo-liberalism since the 1980s as an authoritarian phenomenon,¹⁸ the immediate postwar period is often characterised as one in which democracy is consolidated. But that claim, when made, is then often qualified so much that democracy itself is barely distinguishable from liberalism.¹⁹ It is a markedly constrained form of democracy that emerges: a ‘passive authoritarianism’. (Various shades of authoritarianism will be discussed throughout the chapters, beginning in late Weimar -, when, as Hermann Heller noted, authoritarian government was invoked directly against

¹⁶ For analysis, see Chris Bickerton, ‘The Collapse of Europe’s Mainstream Centre Left’ *New Statesman*, 1 May 2018.

¹⁷ But see Nicos Poulantzas, *State, Power, Socialism* (Verso, 2000), first published in 1978 as *L’etat, le pouvoir, le socialisme* (particularly part four, ‘The Decline of Democracy: Authoritarian Statism’).

¹⁸ See e.g. Ian Bruff (2014) ‘The rise of authoritarian neoliberalism’ *Rethinking Marxism*, vol. 26.

¹⁹ See e.g. Martin Conway, ‘The Rise and Fall of Western Europe’s Democratic Age, 1945-1973’ (2004) 13:1 *Contemporary European History* 67 – 88 (after suggesting that the best approximation of Western Europe between the late 1940’s and early 1970’s would be its ‘democratic age’ he immediately notes that this ‘risks emphasising the strengths rather than the limitations of the rather constrained form of democracy established after the Second World War’, at 71).

democracy, and, specifically, to defend the capitalist form of the economy, - and ending in the euro-crisis phases when democracy is again repressed.²⁰)

‘Authoritarian’ is understood here in opposition and contrast to democratic government and particularly to democratic change, rather than, as is the case in some of the recent literature on the crisis of constitutional democracy, in opposition or contrast to liberal government.²¹ In political theory, notably the republican tradition and various writings in the radical democratic tradition, liberalism (particularly economic liberalism), is frequently described as in tension with democracy.²² Scepticism about the democratic legitimacy of counter-majoritarian institutions is even prevalent amongst self-described liberals.²³

With the aim of a general diagnosis in mind, the postwar reconstitution of Europe, including the project of integration, is presented as, in a significant sense, *conservative*. To be sure, it has taken place ‘in the shadow’ of a federalist vision of European unification.²⁴ But

²⁰ Hermann Heller, ‘Autoritärer Liberalismus’, *Die Neue Rundschau* 44 (1933): 289-298 (in English translation ‘Authoritarian Liberalism?’ *European Law Journal* 21 (2015): 295-301 (translated by S Paulson)). Authoritarianism does not require a charismatic autocratic leadership and the large-scale deployment of extra-legal violence and coercion; it is not the same as Fascism, Dictatorship or Totalitarianism, which is not to say that it cannot lead there (cf. Juan Linz, *Totalitarian and Authoritarian Regimes* (Lynne Rienner Publishers, 2000)).

²¹ For a recent overview of that literature, see Martin Loughlin, ‘The Contemporary Crisis of Constitutional Democracy’ (2019) *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies*. On varieties of authoritarianism, see Günter Frankenberg, ‘Authoritarian Constitutionalism: Coming to Terms with Modernity’s Nightmares’ in Helena Alviar and Günter Frankenberg (eds) *Authoritarian Constitutionalism: Comparative Analysis and Critique* (Elgar 2019).

²² See e.g., Sheldon Wolin, Chantal Mouffe, Cornelius Castoriadis. Jürgen Habermas tries to resolve this tension, but his acknowledgement of it is central to his work. In legal theory, see Brian Tamanaha, ‘The Dark Side of the Relationship between the Rule of Law and Liberalism’ (2008) 33 *NYU Journal of Law and Liberty*.

²³ See e.g. Jeremy Waldron, *Law and Disagreement* (Oxford, Clarendon Press, 1999); ‘Constitutionalism: A Skeptical View’ in T Christiano and J Christman (eds) *Contemporary Debates in Political Philosophy* (Wiley Blackwell, 2009) 267; Richard Bellamy, *Political Constitutionalism: A Republican Defence of the Constitutionality of Democracy* (CUP, 2007). This work, however, tends to be abstracted from political economy and material constitutional development.

²⁴ The progressive federalist vision is often associated with Spinelli’s ‘Ventetone Manifesto’ and the underground resistance movement during the Second World War, but opposed by the governments in exile, especially DeGaulle, who wanted to restore national sovereignty. See also Hannah Arendt, ‘Parties, Movements and Classes (1945) *Partisan Review* 12:4 and discussion in William Selinger, ‘Arendt and European Federalism’ (2016) *Modern Intellectual History* 13:2, 417 – 446. Arendt argues that the collapse of parliamentary government in the interwar period, not only in Germany but across Europe, is a ‘direct and logical consequence of the

this has never been more than a shadow; it has never materialized. In practice, the federalist project was almost immediately defeated. Instead, the constitutional architecture conserves a material order (and *telos*) of economic liberalism, one that was threatened in the interwar period, not only by a militaristic economic protectionism, but also by the prospect, however remote in practice, of democratic socialism - of public or collective control of the economy. To safeguard against this prospect was a concern of both ordoliberalism and neoliberalism.²⁵ It was also a concern, and perhaps with more practical moment, of the Christian Democratic parties that dominated the postwar political scene.

There is, in other words, an uneven but clearly marked de-politicisation (*qua* de-democratization) of the economy written into the postwar reconstitution of Europe.²⁶ To be sure, there was, in the so called *les trente glorieuses*, a significant taming of capitalist excesses, which, in conjunction with the infrastructural rebuilding of war-devastated economies, contributed to a relative equalizing of conditions, as Piketty has documented.²⁷

broader decline of the nation-state', maintaining that the only hope for Europe, 'is to replace national sovereignty with federation', Selinger, at 419.

²⁵ Ordoliberalism will be examined closely in chapter 3. For an early assessment of ordoliberal thinking, see Carl Joachim Friedrich, 'The Political Thought of Neo-liberalism', *American Political Science Review* 49 (1955). It is by now a commonplace that varieties of ordoliberalism and neoliberalism, despite significant differences that will be examined in later chapters, both depend upon a strong state apparatus, partly to guard against politicisation and democratisation of the economy. On their shared certain ideas, and common roots see e.g. P Mirowski and D Plehwe (eds), *The Road from Mont Pelerin: The Making of the Neoliberal Thought Collective* (Harvard University Press, 2009).

²⁶ Alan Milward's classic study, *The European Rescue of the Nation-State* (2nd Ed. Routledge, 2000) presents the Common Market as serving the material needs of the nation-state, working to enhance and maintain its capacity to provide for the security and well-being of its people. European integration was thus ultimately about guaranteeing the renewed legitimacy and viability of the nation-state form. But by the second edition, at the turn of millennium, Milward acknowledges that in internationalising policies, nation-states were trying to 'restrict the force of postwar democratic pressures' at a serious cost to democratic legitimacy.

²⁷ Thomas Piketty, *Capital in the Twenty-First Century* (Cambridge, MA: The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2014). Piketty describes the period between the end of World War II and the beginning of the first oil crisis in 1973 - variously called *les trente glorieuses*, *Wirtschaftswunder* or the Golden Age of Capitalism - as an exceptional one where inequality was contained. But he suggests that the 'fundamental structural contradiction of capitalism' was ameliorated rather than overcome. Capitalism, in other words, continued to adhere to its immanent logic, independent of the politico-legal framework of society. Its effects were mediated

This relative equalization was achieved through varieties of state interventionism, corporate bargaining and social constitutionalism, in conditions of global economic growth. It was not a democratization of the economy, but a moderation of market forces that tamed capitalism; it was a coordinated capitalism or ‘embedded liberalism’ that emerged.²⁸ It emerged not through democratic participation, or an activated citizenry, but through a soft authoritarianism, led by political elites, technocrats and lawyers - domestically as well as through transnational networks.²⁹ It was accompanied by ideological de-radicalisation, the erosion of parliamentarism, and a new political culture dominated by Christian Democracy, replacing ‘the politics of mass mobilisation that had defined the interwar period’ with a political personalism, an ‘individuated politics of interest representation with little purchase on the hearts of many Europeans’.³⁰

From this perspective, the ‘neoliberal’ dynamic beginning in the late 1970’s, continuing at Maastricht and then accelerating in the euro-crisis phase following the financial crisis of 2007-8, reflects a deepening of, rather than a departure from, the previous path of postwar development in general and European integration in particular.³¹ The

by the countervailing forces of redistributive policies and reconstruction in the aftermath of the levelling destruction caused by two world wars. This, however, only enabled “the *illusion* that the fundamental structural contradiction of capitalism ($r > g$) had been overcome” (ibid: 572 (italics added)).

²⁸ The term embedded liberalism, recalling Karl Polanyi, is associated with John Ruggie’s 1982 article, ‘International Regimes, Transactions and Change: Embedded Liberalism in the Postwar Economic Order’ (1982) 26:2 *International Organization*.

²⁹ The centrality of courts and constitutionalisation in preserving elite hegemony and locking in liberal commitments against the vicissitudes of democratic politics gave rise to the term ‘juristocracy’, associated with the work of Ran Hirshl, see e.g. *Towards Juristocracy: The Origins and Consequences of the New Constitutionalism* (Cambridge MA, Harvard University Press, 2004).

³⁰ Bickerton, *European Integration*, above, at 84. This is discussed more fully in chapter 3.

³¹ The claim is therefore similar but also different to Bickerton, who presents the neoliberal turn beginning in the 1970’s as a rupture. To be more precise, Bickerton’s story is told in two acts, in some sense continuous and in others discontinuous. The first act is not the destruction wrought by the conflicts of the first half of the 20th century but the initial stage of European integration itself, during *les trentes glorieuses*, a period of transition between the nation-state and the member-state, which becomes fully-fledged only after the dismantling of the Keynesian welfare state in the 70’s and 80’s. The narrative is complex because Bickerton rejects Milward’s [early] view that the initial phase was based on a democratic policy formation. It was already based on a growing de-politicisation of society, combining class compromise, de-radicalisation of organized labour and

hollowing out of Western democracy, the rise of the juristic and technocratic class, the transformation of the citizen into a consumer, and the escape from political freedom - all can be traced back to postwar reconstruction.³² And in important respects, they constitute a reaction to interwar phenomena.³³

The euro-crisis response confirms this trajectory of 'authoritarian liberalism' and sharpens it. It represents a mutation in the EU's formal constitutional framework, a more pointed political authoritarianism, more coercive and executive in nature, as well as an increasingly asymmetric inter-governmentalism, and even the prospect of German hegemony. Yet this reflects a 'conservative revolution', or 'revolution from above', aimed at shoring up the order of ideas and interests of economic liberalism (including a complex mix of class and national interests).³⁴ The label authoritarian liberalism must now capture this mix, taking into consideration not only the curtailment and evasion of democracy pursued by domestic elites and transnational institutions, but also the increasing spectre of a semi-hegemonic 'German Europe', with Germany as a 'reluctant leader', in a less consensual configuration than in the founding decades of integration.³⁵

Sovereignty and the autonomy of the political

rise of corporatism. But in that case, the continuities seem more significant than the discontinuities, as is argued here. This emphasis on the continuities also distinguishes my claim from Alexander Somek, who presents postwar 'constitutionalism 2.0' as later giving way to a new form of 'constitutionalism 3.0', see *The Cosmopolitan Constitution* (OUP, 2015).

³² On the role of European integration in this dynamic, see D Kelemen, *Eurolegalism: The Transformation of Law and Regulation in the European Union* (HUP 2011)

³³ See R Cristi, *Carl Schmitt and Authoritarian Liberalism: Strong State, Sound Economy* (Cardiff, University of Wales Press, 1997); on the links between Schmitt's interwar writing and neoliberalism, see W Scheuerman, 'The Unholy Alliance of Carl Schmitt and Friedrich A Hayek' (1997) 4:2 *Constellations* 172 - 188.

³⁴ See Etienne Balibar, 'Europe's Revolution from Above', *The Guardian*, 23 November 2011. This is tackled in detail in chapter 5.

³⁵ See Ulrich Beck, *German Europe* (Polity Press, 2013). The complexity of the term 'hegemony', as well as its application to German dominance within the EU, is recently discussed in Perry Anderson, *The H word* (London, Verso, 2017). It will be addressed more fully in chapters 4 and 5.

To translate this claim into the language of constitutional theory requires some unpacking and reframing. The concept of sovereignty can help to do so, as well as provide a longer background thread and fuller historical context. In the modern constitutional imagination, sovereignty is typically said to represent the autonomy of the political from the theological realm.³⁶ This reflects a process of secularisation and modernization of the grounds of political authority. It expresses a new ‘foundational constitutionalism’ that emerged in the wake of the twin revolutionary traditions of late eighteenth century in France and the US. This – by now traditional - model of constitutionalism attributes the authority of the constitution to the consent or authorization, however concretely or abstractly understood, of ‘the people’.³⁷ In principle, it has been said, ‘all modern constitutions begin ‘We the people’’.³⁸

If this claim is viewed in relation to a medieval mindset of divine right, once the word becomes deed, as the rupture of secularization is made flesh in Paris and Philadelphia, political autonomy all but follows as a matter of course. This course does not run entirely smoothly. But apart from the exceptional event of totalitarianism in the twentieth century, representing a return of religious absolutism in a different form, the modern constitutional path of liberal democracy is presented as the culmination of secular progress à la Hegel.³⁹

³⁶ See Martin Loughlin, ‘Why Sovereignty?’ in *Sovereignty and Law: Domestic, Regional and Global Perspectives* (ed Rawlings, Leyland and Young, Oxford Hart Publishing, 2013) 34.

³⁷ This foundational constitutionalism might be associated in Europe with the work of Dieter Grimm, see e.g. ‘Does Europe Need a Constitution?’ (1995) 1 *European Law Journal* 282; ‘The Constitution in the Process of Denationalisation’ (2005) 12 *Constellations* 447; ‘The Achievements of Constitutionalism and its Prospects in a Changed World’ in Loughlin and Dobner (eds), *The Twilight of Constitutionalism* (Oxford: OUP, 2010).

³⁸ Simone Chambers, ‘Democracy, Popular Sovereignty and Constitutional Legitimacy’ (2003) 11 *Constellations* 153. As Neil Walker notes, modern constitutionalism ‘helped create new form of sovereignty rather than simply reign in an old form’, in ‘Sovereignty and Beyond: The Double Edge of External Constitutionalism’ (2018) 58 *Virginia Journal of International Law*.

³⁹ The end of history thesis is more recently associated with Francis Fukuyama, and he has since abandoned it. But the basic secularization thesis is at the core of a French tradition of political thought that includes Marcel Gauchet, Claude Lefort, and Pierre Rosanvallon. This makes up a so-called ‘anti-totalitarian’ position, which

This triumph is fully complete as the Soviet exception is extinguished with the collapse of the USSR toward the end of the millennium, consecrated by a new 'end of history thesis' (since discarded by its author) and triumph of liberal capitalism (and if the USSR is merely an anomaly, the completion of history can be dated much earlier).

However, this view of modern constitutionalism in the narrow light of a secularization thesis, based on the differentiation of the political from the religious, elides the action of constitutional development: the domain of political economy. If the autonomy of the political is presented as a *material struggle*, not merely or not even primarily for secularization but for equality (or as Etienne Balibar puts it, 'Equaliberty'), set against the premodern fusion of political and economic power, the path of modern constitutionalism is immediately illuminated.⁴⁰ The continuous if uneven struggle for political equality, universal suffrage and social rights, including women's movements, worker's movements, and – broadening the horizon - anti-colonial movements is then highlighted.⁴¹

The 'march of the masses onto the stage of history' that begins in the late 18th and continues through the 19th century, reaches a climax in the interwar era, a crucial turning point in constitutional history, a point at which political democracy is expanded, and there are calls for it to be extended to the economy, at the same time as capitalism experiences its most significant moments of crisis culminating with the global depression of the early 1930's. In these critical moments, democratic capitalism, to adopt Wolfgang Streeck's terminology, appears unfeasible because of the heightened tension between its two poles, one demanding democratic solidarity and social protection, the other demanding market rationality and

theorises the autonomy of the political without sufficient regard to material forces. See further, Michael A. Wilkinson 'Public Law and the Autonomy of the Political: A Material Critique' in Wilkinson and Dowdle (eds) *Questioning the Foundations of Public Law* (Hart, 2018)

⁴⁰ See Etienne Balibar, *Equaliberty: Political Essays* (Duke University Press, Durham, 2014).

⁴¹ The allure of the project of postnational constitutionalism, and its political counterpart, the DiEM movement, is that it seems to be a continuation of this modern project of democratization, taking the inclusionary dynamic a step further, beyond national borders. But for an alternative critical narrative of modernization, see e.g. James Tully 'The Unfreedom of the Moderns in Comparison to Their Ideals of Constitutional Democracy' (2002) 65:2 *Modern Law Review* 204 – 228.

commodification. This polarity is represented by the extraordinary growth in inequality on the one hand, and an increasing class consciousness on the other – both with the organisation of the working class and with the high concentration of capital through monopolization and cartelisation.⁴² The state (through its governing institutions) has to act more coercively to maintain liberal economic order, in combination of its repression of domestic labour and expansion of imperial ambitions abroad. Because it so conspicuously enters the fray, extinguishing the myth of the ‘neutral’ or ‘nightwatchman’ state of classical liberal imagination, the material constitution comes more fully into view.⁴³ One or the other – democracy or capitalism - has to give.

As Hermann Heller diagnosed in 1932, just before the Nazis gained power, it was democracy that was set aside: liberalism became authoritarian through a series of Presidential Cabinets ruling late Weimar through decree, via emergency powers granted by the Constitution.⁴⁴ This curtailment of parliament and of democratic freedoms was the prelude to democracy’s full-scale collapse soon after, with the Nazi seizure of power in 1933 marking the end of the Weimar Republic, not, it should be noted, and contrary to a dominant constitutional myth, in conditions of democratic excess, but of democratic suppression.⁴⁵

The material constitution

⁴² See Wolfgang Streeck, ‘The Crises of Democratic Capitalism’ (2011) 71 *New Left Review* 5 – 29; Wolfgang Streeck, *Buying Time: The Delayed Crisis of Democratic Capitalism* (Verso, 2013)

⁴³ For an earlier attempt to dispel the myth of the weak liberal state, see Franz Neumann, ‘The Change in Function of Law in Modern Society’ in *The Political and the Authoritarian State* (New York, Free Press, 1957) 22-68.

⁴⁴ Hermann Heller, ‘Autoritärer Liberalismus’, *Die Neue Rundschau* 44 (1933): 289-298 (in English translation ‘Authoritarian Liberalism?’ *European Law Journal* 21 (2015): 295-301 (translated by S Paulson)). This is examined in chapter 2.

⁴⁵ This is examined in detail in chapter 2. For a recent recycling of this myth see e.g. J. H. H. Weiler, ‘The European Circumstance and the Politics of Meaning: Not on Bread Alone Doth Man Liveth (Deut. 8:3; Mat 4:4)’ (2020) 21 *German Law Journal* 96 – 99 (‘Hitler and Mussolini were hugely popular at their time and came to power democratically’).

It is no surprise that the idea of the ‘material constitution’ surfaces in the interwar period, in the minds of both conservative and socialist scholars: the crisis of parliamentarism had exposed the instability of liberal constitutionalism in the face of competing political claims and the fragmentation and polarization of social forces.⁴⁶ And it is no surprise that material analysis has again begun to recapture the attention, after the most recent crisis of democratic capitalism has cast established institutions and the standard assumptions of their legitimacy into serious doubt.

But, by the present conjuncture, the ‘foundational constitutionalism’ of the French and American revolutionary traditions had already given way to a ‘freestanding constitutionalism’ driven by the motor of economism and the ideology (or utopianism) of individual human rights.⁴⁷ This constitutional discourse, driven by the material dynamic of global capital and the normative project of liberal individualism, had been the accompaniment to the gradual loss of any collective, democratic, understanding of the constituent power.⁴⁸ That meant that when crises recently struck in Europe (and elsewhere) there was a political vacuum into which claims now frequently characterized - and often too casually dismissed - as politically populist would easily be channeled.⁴⁹

The democratic ground had been vacated by decades of freestanding constitutionalism, with the displacement of the idea of constituent power and a politics of ‘extreme centrism’ substituting even ordinary political contestation.⁵⁰ This was a period in

⁴⁶ From Carl Schmitt, Eric Voegelin, and Constantino Mortati on the conservative authoritarian wing, to Antonio Gramsci on the radical wing via Hermann Heller in the social democratic centre (see Goldoni and Wilkinson, above, for discussion).

⁴⁷ On ‘freestanding constitutionalism’ in the European Union, in contrast to the foundational constitutionalism of the modern revolutionary tradition, see Michael Wilkinson, ‘Political Constitutionalism and the European Union’ (2013) 76:2 *Modern Law Review* 191 – 222.

⁴⁸ See Samuel Moyn, *The Last Utopia: Human Rights in History* (Harvard University Press, 2010).

⁴⁹ See e.g. Jan-Werner Müller, *What is Populism?* (University of Pennsylvania Press, 2016)

⁵⁰ The phrase was used by Tariq Ali to capture the neoliberal consensus among political elites in the UK after 1989 (T Ali, *The Extreme Centre: A Warning* (London, Verso, 2015). On extreme centrism as a phenomenon of

which, in significant part due to the EU's own constitutional structure, there was a further 'hollowing out' of democracy, reflected in the emergence of a 'void' between rulers and ruled, as centre-left and centre-right merged in practice and ideology.⁵¹ It also left the space open for new hybrids to emerge, inflections of authoritarian liberalism incorporating an uneasy but not unsuccessful mix of technocracy and populism.⁵²

The discourse of 'reclaiming sovereignty' so prominent in the euro-crisis and in the Brexit debate then seems to make much more sense (which is not to say that it will necessarily be realised). It is not that sovereignty had been lost by a return to the shackles of religious truth, however much one might like to think of Brussels bureaucrats as the high priests of Europe. It is that sovereignty has been perceived to have been lost through the erosion of democratic control over the economy.⁵³ 'Perceived' is an important word here. Constitutions do not exist only as norms; they exist in a universe where facts and norms are interrelated. They have a material existence, which is internally related to their formal prescriptions and proscriptions and which depends in part upon the plausibility of their claims to political unity, the strength of their institutions and social supports, the desirability and feasibility of their political objectives. And care should be taken to highlight that democratic control does not necessarily equal effective control, at least in the short term.⁵⁴ This is borne out by the Greek crisis – the economic cost of leaving the single

European integration, see Michael A. Wilkinson, 'The Brexit Referendum and the Crisis of Extreme Centristism' (2016) *German Law Journal*.

⁵¹ On the role of Europe in this process of de-politicisation, see Peter Mair, *Ruling the Void* (Verso 2013) 115 – 119.

⁵² See e.g. C Accetti and C Bickerton, 'Populism and Technocracy: Opposites or Complements?' (2017) 20:2 *Critical Review of International Social and Political Philosophy* 186 – 206.

⁵³ On the erosion of sovereignty in the euro-crisis phase, see Martin Loughlin, 'The Erosion of Sovereignty' (2016) 45:2 *Netherlands Journal of Legal Philosophy* 57 – 81. The argument presented in this book traces this process of erosion back several decades earlier.

⁵⁴ The implication is not, it should be stressed, that leaving the EU or the eurozone would lift the material constraints on the democratic political process. Constraints would remain, not least the financial markets and geo-political pressures that exist in a state-system of radically unequal units. Neither would leaving the EU necessarily lead to the re-democratisation of the economy. It may simply be controlled by a different set of

currency, aside from the legal-technical obstacles, may have been considered practically prohibitive of any radical reclaiming of monetary and fiscal sovereignty that might follow an exit of the euro area.⁵⁵ But in an era when virtually all constitutions pay at least lip service to the idea of democratic self-determination, withholding economic decisions from electoral contestation must overcome a high threshold of political justification, if it can be justified at all. The postwar justification, broadly understood as an attempt to regain liberal democratic and economic stability, can no longer hold even on its own terms; anti-systemic forces have returned and instability beckons.

The material conception of sovereignty advanced here is captured in a different discursive tradition of constituent power, one revived in the 1990's by Antonio Negri.⁵⁶ With the modern constitutional revolution, 'the people' do not of a sudden become the source of authority, not in anything other than a purely symbolic sense. The real material struggles over constituent power unfold over time, in ebbs and flows, and across critical and even revolutionary moments (not only 1789, but also the revolutions of 1848, 1870, and 1918, the general strike of 1926, the unrest of 1968, the Occupy movements beginning in 2011). These involve class conflicts, identity conflicts, and (if we broaden the horizon) anti-imperial struggles - conflicts of material distribution as well as political recognition.⁵⁷ Struggles for constituent power may begin as informal social movements, becoming more formally channeled by political parties, as in the case of workers' rights, and more recently in the extraordinary rise (and decline) of Syriza in Greece. Their demands may become institutionalised, as with the inclusion of material social demands into a political

elites. Whether to leave or remain in the EU is a complex political judgment, and no more will be said about it here.

⁵⁵ For an argument for Greece leaving the euro see Costas Lapavistas and Heiner Flassbeck, *Against the Troika: Crisis and Austerity in the Eurozone* (Verso Books, 2015)

⁵⁶ See Antonio Negri, *Insurgencies: Constituent Power and the Modern State* (University of Minnesota Press, 1999). Later this material-historical approach appears to be abandoned by Negri in favour of a global 'multitude', as we will see in Part III.

⁵⁷ On the variety of anti-capitalist boundary struggles, see Nancy Fraser, 'Behind Marx's Hidden Abode: For an Expanded Conception of Capitalism' (2014) 86 *New Left Review* 55-72

programme or even a constitutional text or international agreement. They may become juridified, in the form of social rights, with all the accompanying difficulties of application due to the obstacles in the way of courts giving effect to redistributive demands.⁵⁸ But they may also be obstructed or repressed, by formal constitutional means and informal, ideological and coercive strategies, such as in the refrain that there is no alternative to neoliberal structural reform (TINA), in the constitutionalisation of austerity through judicial interpretation of the European Treaties in the euro-crisis phase or in the coercion and cajoling of debtor countries by formal and informal groupings in the same period.⁵⁹ To capture constitutional change is not only to take account of its formal channeling but of constitutionalism's framing function, the way a constitution (understood broadly) establishes how political debate is to be organized and what its limits are.⁶⁰

With this material understanding in mind, we can briefly present the postwar reconstitution of the European state and state-system as not only conservative but also essentially *reactionary* in character, not only (and perhaps not even) to prevent society from turning toward fascism but to prevent it from obtaining material control over the relations and forces of production.⁶¹ This is expressed ideologically in the vesting of sovereignty in 'the constitution' rather than 'the people', and in having the values of the constitution

⁵⁸ For discussion see Emiliios Christodoulidis, 'Social Rights Constitutionalism: An Antagonistic Endorsement' (2017) 44:1 *Journal of Law and Society* 123 - 149

⁵⁹ Cf. Clemens Kaupa, *The Pluralist Character of the European Economic Constitution* (Hart Publishing, 2016).

⁶⁰ As Gavin Anderson puts it, 'constitutional discourse is always more than the rules it generates or legitimates..., setting the parameters not just for how politics is contested, but what is deemed politically contestable' (see G. Anderson, in S Gill, *New Constitutionalism and World Order* (Cambridge, CUP, 2015) 283, quoting Emiliios Christodoulidis).

⁶¹ Note that the focus here is on the project of European integration as culminating in the European Union, officially born at Maastricht but similar story of conservative counter-revolution could be told about the European Convention on Human Rights (see e.g. Marco Duranti, *The Conservative Human Rights Revolution: European Identity, Transnational Politics, and the Origin of the European Convention* (OUP, 2017)). That story is compatible with what is told here, and partly intertwined, but the overall material significance of the EU is thought to far outweigh that of the ECHR.

guarded by so-called ‘independent institutions’ - independent of democratic will but not of liberal economic practices and ideas, indeed often legally or even constitutionally bound to them. It may even be entrenched, as in the German case, by the ‘eternity clause’, attempting to make the sovereignty of the constitution unbreakable (ironically given its prominence, the German basic law was not even a proper constitution and was meant to have been reconstituted with German reunification).⁶² The idea of the sovereignty of the constitution or even the sovereignty of law, which epitomize this transformation, has a reach far beyond Germany, often representing a broader moralization of constitutional theory and liberal judicial politics itself.⁶³ Underpinning this transformation is the belief that the people are no longer trusted to rule, not only by elites, but also by the people themselves: ‘We are afraid of the people’, to adopt Möllers’ apt expression.⁶⁴

As the idea of the constitution as a basic and freestanding social contract gains ascendancy, it is not only ‘the people’ but also ‘the state’ that fades into the background in the minds of constitutional scholars (liberal and otherwise), wholly disarming them for its return in the recent conjuncture, when it is again called to act in order to maintain or regain order, if now in light of an inter-state system that, in the case of the EU, suffers legitimization crises of its own.⁶⁵

⁶² See Werner Heun, *The Constitution of Germany* (Hart, 2010). The ‘never again’ narrative was only later read into this provisional and organisational document, as Michaela Hailbronner shows, see *Traditions and Transformation: The Rise of German Constitutionalism* (OUP, 2015).

⁶³ This turn is often inspired by Ronald Dworkin’s legal theory, e.g., in the work of Matthias Kumm, examined in chapter 4.

⁶⁴ Christoph Möllers, “‘We are (afraid of) the People’: Constituent Power in German Constitutionalism’ in Martin Loughlin and Neil Walker (eds.) *The Paradox of Constitutionalism: Constituent Power and Constitutional Form* (Oxford University Press, 2007) 87-107. Already in 1950, Franz Neumann wrote about the ‘German’s propensity to safeguard themselves against democracy through the means of jurisdiction and the provision of fixed basic rights’ and described their ‘constitutional fetishism’ (see Clara Maier, ‘The Weimar Origins of the West German *Rechtsstaat*, 1919 – 1969’ (2019) 62:4 *The Historical Journal* 1081). More generally, see Michael Mandel, ‘A Brief History of the New Constitutionalism, or “How we Changed Everything so that Everything Would Remain the Same”’ (1998) 32:2 *Israeli Law Review* 250 – 300.

⁶⁵ For an overview of the waxing and waning of the concept of the state in constitutional theory, see H. Patrick Glenn, *The Cosmopolitan State* (OUP, 2013) ch 1. Note that there are important exceptions to the recent decline in attention to the state in constitutional theory, see e.g. Martin Loughlin, ‘In defense of *Staatslehre*’ (2010) *Der*

The constitutionalisation of EU law

This material transformation is accompanied by a new constitutional imaginary, which emerges in domestic settings as well as through the project of European integration.⁶⁶ The EU exaggerates and radicalizes these tendencies, not least with the gradual authorization of an unwritten European ‘constitution’ by ‘we, the court’.⁶⁷ The disappearance of the democratic constituent power occurs not all at once, but in a gradual and incremental process of ‘constitutionalisation’.⁶⁸ This happens across various phases, beginning with the early years after the Treaty of Rome, when lawyer-activists were central to the project of forging a European constitution through instrumentalising the judicial architecture created by the Treaty. This project would be reinforced with the Single European Act in 1986 and up-scaled to the macro-economic constitution of Economic and Monetary Union at Maastricht.⁶⁹ Constitutionalisation reached an anticlimactic pinnacle with the Constitutional Treaty project in the new millennium, failing in referenda in France and the Netherlands in 2005. The constitutional idea was then formally abandoned, along with some of the symbolic accouterments, but its content was repacked in its essentials with the Treaty

Staat (and more generally, *Foundations of Public Law* (OUP, 2012)). But a corollary of the fact that the state disappears in much legal and constitutional theory is perhaps that talk of a European federal state also dies in European studies (with Federico Mancini a rare exception in the mid-1990’s), replaced by discourses of constitutional pluralism.

⁶⁶ Of course, this has significant national variations. On the German context, see R Ptak, ‘Neoliberalism in Germany: Revisiting the Ordoliberal Foundations of the Social Market Economy’ in Mirowski and Plehwe (eds), above. On the European economic constitution, see W Sauter, ‘The Economic Constitution of the European Union’ (1998) *Columbia Journal of European Law* 27

⁶⁷ See Miguel Maduro’s, *We The Court: The European Court of Justice and the European Economic Constitution* (Hart, 1998).

⁶⁸ See Martin Loughlin, ‘What is Constitutionalisation?’ in Loughlin and Dobner (eds) *The Twilight of Constitutionalism* (OUP, 2009).

⁶⁹ See Vauchez, Cohen above.

of Lisbon,⁷⁰ and the normative and explanatory appeal of constitutional discourse in the scholarship barely diminished.⁷¹

The cumulative effect of constitutionalisation in these phases and especially in the post-Maastricht construction of EMU was transformative, by delinking the sovereign powers of the state (especially the power to control money) from the constituent power of the people. This is a foundational shift, because central to the modern constitutional imagination had always been not only that the powers of the state must be limited (as liberalism recommends), but that they be limited in the name of ‘the people’ or at least recognizable as a process of collective *self*-limitation (as popular sovereignty demands). In the postwar constitution, deepened and entrenched at Maastricht, by contrast, the powers of the state are constrained, not by ‘the people’ — but by ‘the market’ and the interstate system, by institutions that are technocratic rather than democratically responsive and that are geared to replicating or restoring, as far as possible, market rationality.⁷²

The constitutionalisation of economic liberalism is not a static settlement, establishing a clear demarcation of the political and the economic for the future. On the contrary, due to the dynamics underpinning neo- and ordoliberal development, there is no neat separation of economic and political spheres because market logic tends to expand and extend, dominating the whole of political society, not only the economy narrowly

⁷⁰ For analysis, see Christine Reh, ‘The Lisbon Treaty: De-Constitutionalising the EU’ (2009) 47:3 *JCMS* 625 - 650

⁷¹ The literature on EU constitutionalism is too voluminous to cite here and has not ceased in productivity. There are textbooks and even entire journals dedicated to exploring EU in constitutional terms e.g. *The European Constitutional Law Review*. For exceptions to those who embrace the constitutionalist discourse, see Peter Lindseth, *Power and Legitimacy: Reconciling Europe and the Nation-State* (OUP, 2010), Bruno de Witte, ‘The EU As International Legal Experiment’ in Deburca and Weiler (eds.) *The Worlds of European Constitutionalism* (CUP, 2011). Weiler himself claimed to be a skeptic despite doing so much to spread the idea.

⁷² Bickerton, above, 67. See also Wolfgang Streeck, ‘Markets and Peoples: Democratic Capitalism and European Integration’ (2013) 73 *New Left Review* 63 - 71.

conceived.⁷³ As Isiksel notes on the EU's own constitutional evolution, 'the expansion of the EU's operations has engendered the colonization of ever greater swathes of public policy by institutions designed primarily to create and govern a supranational market.'⁷⁴ This has occurred through political decisions and constitutional changes.

An obvious objection to characterising these processes as authoritarian can be anticipated. In a trivial sense, membership of the EU remains a voluntary surrender of authority; states can, after all (at least since Lisbon) formally leave the EU, now in accordance with Article 50 TEU and whatever domestic constitutional procedures are required. But this formalism misses precisely that the process of European integration is one of state and constitutional *transformation*, a change in domestic political institutions and elites (ruling arrangements) as well as in the social constitutional imaginary (the ruling relationship).⁷⁵ It sets limits to what is politically possible or at least what is politically feasible within current constitutional constraints, which of course may themselves change over time. The nature and extent of these limits, and their likelihood of change, does to some extent depend on which of the 'variety of constitutionalisms' adverted to above we are concerned with, and in particular on whether a Member State of the EU is also a member of the euro area. Britain can leave the EU in a way that would not be open to a country in the eurozone. Within the eurozone, the 'variety of constitutionalisms', along with a variety of capitalisms, has been reduced to a singular logic through the euro-crisis phase, although in fact this narrowing of political economic rationality can be traced back further.⁷⁶

Crisis, without doubt, has opened up the possibility of critique; this has led, in the case of Brexit, to the first significant possibility of rupture, and an undoing of the postwar

⁷³ In the critical literature on International Relations, under the label of the 'new constitutionalism', this claim is relatively well-established, see e.g. S Gill, *Power and Resistance in the New World Order* (Basingstoke and New York, Palgrave Macmillan, 2003).

⁷⁴ Turkuler Isiksel, *Europe's Functional Constitutionalism* (Oxford University Press, 2016) 19.

⁷⁵ This is one way of understanding the acknowledgement in Miller, see *R v Secretary of State for Exiting the European Union* [2017] UKSC 5.

⁷⁶ As we will discuss in Parts III and IV, the 'variety of capitalisms' literature is of limited explanatory purchase when confronted with the interconnections among various models of political economy.

constitutional settlement in Europe.⁷⁷ It is an event of considerable moment and may yet brook momentum for a broader unraveling of the project. But because of the UK's particular material relation with the EU, it may be an outlier. Rupture remains a distant prospect in the core of Europe as well as in the periphery.

The difficulties of Brexit show that even outside of the single currency the material constraints of membership and the costs of exiting (or the perception of such) are very real, as is the significance of membership of the EU in the constitutional imagination. For a core country, such as Germany, France or Italy, to leave the EU would signal a material constitutional change, perhaps even a revolutionary one, even if formally permissible as a matter of legal logic.

Authoritarian populism?

From the present vantage point, the instability of the postwar settlement – considered less than two decades ago as symbolizing a ‘model for the nations of the world in the 21st century’,⁷⁸ - now comes into full view. Europe finds itself, once again, in a critical condition following the global financial crisis.⁷⁹ Movements outside of the established centre have returned, and arguments for reclaiming sovereignty over borders, over people and over capital, have been resurrected. There has been much discussion about the phenomena of right-wing nationalism in Hungary and, more recently, Poland, and of left-wing parties in Greece and Spain that have grown out of anti-austerity movements. But the reshaping of the political landscape has occurred not only in peripheral countries devastated by the economic crisis but in the core of Europe, and in creditor nations. In the 2017 Federal

⁷⁷ As explained above, the UK represents an atypical material position from the viewpoint of European integration as a whole, making it difficult to generalize the Brexit phenomenon. But the signs of discontent with the EU are widespread.

⁷⁸ See Mark Leonard, *Why Europe Will Run the 21st Century* (Fourth Estate, 2005).

⁷⁹ Not long into the crisis, French philosopher Etienne Balibar described Europe as looking like a ‘dead’ political project, see ‘Europe: Final Crisis? Some Theses’ (2010) *Theory and Event*.

elections, a far-right party, the *Alternative für Deutschland*, entered the German parliament for the first time since the Second World War. The French Presidential elections of the same year pitted Emmanuel Macron, leading a new formation *en Marche*, against Marine Le Pen of the *Front Nationale*. In Italy the following year, the refusal to appoint a Eurosceptic finance minister provoked a mini-constitutional crisis after the 2018 election produced a coalition between the right-wing *Lega* and the centrist-populist *Five Star Movement*.

The soft authoritarian liberalism of the pre-crisis period, hardened through the crisis response, is now accompanied by an authoritarian populism that looks set to stay. The Polanyian double movement, in reaction to enforced, coerced or elite-led marketization and commodification, takes the form of a conservative rather than progressive backlash, with politically illiberal features, in particular with regard to freedom of the press and attitudes towards immigration.⁸⁰ This is all occurring from within the European Union and potentially poses a greater challenge to the project than the voluntary exit of the UK.

Significantly, the authoritarian populist reaction in Central and Eastern Europe to the brisk transition to market capitalism following accession to the EU, an inflection of rather than rupture from neoliberal economics, has been permitted if not indulged; whereas the ‘progressive’ response – an attempt to break with neoliberal austerity in Greece from the left – was harshly punished, if ultimately self-immolated with Syriza’s capitulation.⁸¹ The movement towards populism pre-dated the euro-crisis proper, growing in the ‘core of

⁸⁰ Karl Polanyi, *The Great Transformation: The Political and Economic Origins of Our Time* (Beacon Press 2001 [1944]). Polanyi’s theory is examined in chapter 3.

⁸¹ The turn to ‘authoritarian populism’ in Eastern Europe has been described as continuing many of the policies of economic neoliberalism. See Gareth Dale and A Fabry, ‘Neoliberalism in Eastern Europe and the Former Soviet Union’ in D Cahill, M Cooper, M Konings and D Pimrose (eds) *The Sage Handbook of Neoliberalism* (Sage Publications 2018). On the link between financial crisis in Hungary, the imposition of austerity and a populist turn, see Claire Kilpatrick, ‘Constitutions, Social Rights and Sovereign Debt States in Europe: A Challenging New Area of Constitutional Inquiry’ (2015) EUI Working Paper LAW No 2015/34. Habermas described the approach to Greece as punishment for Syriza daring to contest austerity from the left, see Philip Altermann, ‘Jürgen Habermas’ verdict on the EU/Greece Debt Deal - Full Transcript’, *The Guardian*, 16th July 2015.

Europe' in the post-Maastricht phase, purporting to fill the 'void' that had emerged in the decades of passive authoritarian liberalism.

With the blame for authoritarian populism now being laid by the ruling classes, as well as much of the academic commentary, on an excess of democracy rather than a deficit, political and constitutional elites double-down on authoritarian projects of integration. Ordoliberalism is declared the only game in town;⁸² those who contest it are caricatured as un-European, constituting the 'enemy within' the European Union.⁸³ Increasingly there are also signs of a new 'enemy without' emerging, as Russia assumes a new geopolitical significance in the liberal imagination but not yet one that could unite foreign policy across the Continent.⁸⁴ If populism itself is simply derided, often dismissed in a careless and undifferentiated manner, its rhetoric is emulated by European elites, in an attempt to co-opt its appeal.⁸⁵

An incidental feature of this study is that by illustrating the constitutional depths of the present conjuncture, the seriousness of the stakes are underlined: to break with European integration is not merely to mark a break with neoliberal political economy, but with liberal constitutionalism. Where this conjuncture leads remains to be seen; the situation is fluid, the long period of crisis beginning in 2008 is as yet unresolved. It could

⁸² See 'The Donald Tusk interview', 16th July, 2015 in the FT, 'Greece: Donald Tusk warns of extremist political contagion' <https://www.ft.com/content/f6872342-2bd2-11e5-acfb-cbd2e1c81cca>; Mario Draghi, noting that the 'monetary constitution of the ECB is firmly grounded in the principles of ordoliberalism', see 'Opening Remarks at the Session "Rethinking the Limitations of Monetary Policy", Speech by Mario Draghi, The Isreal Museum, Jerusalem, 18 June, 2013, available at <https://www.ecb.europa.eu/press/key/date/2013/html/sp130618.en.html>

⁸³ See e.g. Udo di Fabio, 'Karlsruhe Makes a Referral' (2014) 15 *German Law Journal* 107

⁸⁴ It is notable that in the Habermas/Derrida initiative launched in 2003, in response to the invasion of Iraq, it was the US that played the Schmittian foil to European humanism, see 'February 15th or What Binds European Together?' (2003) 10 *Constellations* 291.

⁸⁵ As with Commission President Von der Leyen's attempt in designating a portfolio to defending a 'European Way of Life', <https://www.politico.eu/article/von-der-leyen-on-european-way-of-life-we-cant-let-others-take-away-our-language/>

offer a return to a democratic path that had largely been abandoned over the last decades, and to all the opportunities and risks that come with it. But this is far from guaranteed.

The outline of the book

The narrative will unfold across five Parts. **Part I** examines the interwar breakdown of liberal democracy, when ruling elites turned to an authoritarian liberalism in a failed attempt to shore up a system in crisis. The story begins in Weimar Germany (chapter 1), not only because this sharpens the perspective but because of Weimar's legacy for the postwar period. But authoritarian liberalism is also presented as a more general phenomenon, extending 'beyond Weimar' (chapter 2).

Postwar Europe is then examined more fully in **Part II**, as its inter-state, state-society and social relations are reconstituted in such a way as to gradually restrain sovereignty, de-politicise the economy and de-radicalise politics. This occurs through various inter-state (chapter 3), institutional (chapter 4) and societal changes (chapter 5). These are the result of domestic constitutional projects, supranational projects of European constitutionalisation (particularly the process of 'integration through law'), and the ascendancy of ordoliberalism and neoliberalism in the constitutional imagination, buttressed by the political demobilization of the masses.

Part III charts the road from Maastricht to Lisbon, when further integration starts to be accompanied by various counter-movements. The period after the fall of the Berlin Wall marks the return of the 'German question' but also a 'new intergovernmentalism' (chapter 6). EU authority is extended to new areas but increasingly contested, notably by the German constitutional court, although contestation is evident in political arenas across Europe (chapter 7). The differentiation of the political and the economic is scaled up through Economic and Monetary Union, imposing additional external constraint on sovereign power, and market rationality is deepened across a wider and more heterogeneous European constitutional space (chapter 8).

In the euro-crisis phase, examined in **Part IV**, the constitutional configuration is sustained only by further intervention and the harsher disciplining of member states. This

occurs through an increasingly asymmetrical inter-governmental formation which raises the spectre of German hegemony (chapter 9). The significance of non-democratic transnational institutions, particularly the ECB, becomes more conspicuous, but these are only able to defer rather than resolve deep-seated structural problems (chapter 10). Asymmetrical state interventions and institutional innovations are also accompanied by significant counter-movements, offering, but ultimately failing, to reclaim popular sovereignty and democratic control over the economy (chapter 11).

In conclusion, the 'new' phenomenon of authoritarian populism is considered, and judged to present an inflection of authoritarian liberalism rather than a rupture.

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Michael Wilkinson is Associate Professor in the Department of Law, London School of Economics and Political Science
E-mail: M.Wilkinson@lse.ac.uk

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iCourts
- The Danish National Research Foundation's Centre of Excellence for International Courts
The Faculty of Law
University of Copenhagen
Karen Blixens Plads 16
2300 Copenhagen S
E-mail: icourts@jur.ku.dk
Tel. +45 35 32 26 26